

Interference-aware Distributed Precoding in Coherent Large-scale Distributed MIMO

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Abstract—Large-scale Distributed Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (D-MIMO) is one of the key radio technologies to support ubiquitous radio access by enabling the User Equipment (UE) having simultaneous connectivity to many highly coordinated network transmission points called Access Points (APs). In this work, coherent large-scale D-MIMO has been investigated in an industrial indoor scenario considering the frequency range from 3.5 GHz to 100 GHz assuming synchronized APs. The UE-centric AP selection has been studied to determine the subset of APs jointly serving to the UEs. Thereafter, interference aware distributed precoding is formulated and compared with centralized precoding. The simulation results show that more coordinated APs in clusters increases coherent precoding gain and enhances interference management, eventually provides more gain in spectral efficiency. Moreover, distributed, partially distributed and collocated deployment models have been compared, and trade-off between implementation complexity and deployment complexity has been shown.

Index Terms—Distributed MIMO, UE-centric, AP selection, precoding, zero forcing, 6G.

I. INTRODUCTION

Beyond 5G and 6G networks provide way-out levels of connectivity and Quality of Service (QoS) to cope with the never-ending number of connected User Equipments (UEs) and the huge increase in data-rate demand. One of the traditional ways of meeting the data-rate requirements of each UE in beyond 5G and 6G systems is to increase the number of Base Stations (BSs) with very large number of antenna elements called massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (mMIMO). However, small cell densification without any coordination does not scale due to the inter-cell interference which significantly degrades the performance [1].

Large-scale distributed MIMO (D-MIMO), which can be thought of as combination of ultra dense networks and coordinated multi-point transmission, is now regarded as a potential physical-layer paradigm shift for beyond 5G systems [2]. Unlike general cases where the BS surrounded by the UEs, in D-MIMO, each UE is surrounded by several geographically distributed Access Points (APs) connected to a Central Processing Unit (CPU) through high-capacity fronthaul links (e.g., fiber-optic cables) [1]. In such a system, each UE experiences being in the center of the cell composed of many APs in their proximity and does not experience any fixed cell boundaries, the path attenuation is significantly reduced since the APs get closer to the UEs, high probability of line-of-sight removes

blocking. Consequently, D-MIMO provides significant gains when densification starts to suffer from interference, thus, uniform coverage and extreme performance everywhere thanks to macro diversity to meet the QoS requirements established for beyond 5G and 6G networks [3].

A. Related Work

Recent studies have considered D-MIMO network which is also known as cell-free massive MIMO systems. D-MIMO networks have been shown to outperform traditional small-cell and cellular massive MIMO networks in several practical scenarios [1], [4], [5]. The performance of D-MIMO has also been analyzed under several realistic network and hardware assumptions, e.g., with hybrid analog-digital precoding [6], under channel non-reciprocity [7]. In [3], authors investigated the potential of D-MIMO networks while addressing practical deployment issues to deal with the increased overhead on the fronthaul derived from the signal co-processing. Authors in [8] provided a comprehensive study and introduced receive combining and transmit precoding schemes with centralized/distributed operations. In [9], authors proposed a precoding algorithm considering overlapping clusters of APs and power control in a centralized manner. Authors in [10] studied dynamic cooperation cluster framework in cell-free Massive MIMO to identify and address scalability issues and provide distributed algorithms for initial access, pilot assignment, cluster formation, precoding, and combining. In [11], authors proposed two distributed precoding schemes providing interference cancelation without additional fronthauling overhead that can be implemented by APs with few antenna elements. Motivated by the practical implementation of cell-free massive MIMO, various AP selection schemes are introduced in [12], [13], [14]. Furthermore, authors in [15] proposed a user association procedure in a cell-free massive MIMO system where the users are served by a subset of APs in the network, and showed that the method offers a considerably lower backhaul load with a negligible performance loss.

B. Contribution

Given that each UE can associate with any AP using Joint Transmission (JT) in a UE-centric manner, i.e., without fixed cell borders, this work presents the following contributions:

Fig. 1. Illustration of AP deployment and clustering.

- Interference Aware Distributed Zero Forcing (IADZF) method has been applied and compared with Centralized Zero Forcing (CZF) method which is conducted throughout the network.
- The performance of large-scale D-MIMO systems is evaluated for single-AP selection, UE-centric AP-cluster JT and all-AP JT in a downlink industrial indoor scenario where blockage effect is in the propagation environment, considering a frequency range from sub-6 GHz to sub-THz.
- It has been shown that IADZF with AP-clustering can achieve the performance of centralized precoding while more coordinated APs in clusters increases coherent precoding gain and enhances interference management, eventually provides more gain in Spectral Efficiency (SE).
- Distributed, partially distributed and collocated deployment models have been compared, and trade-off between implementation complexity and deployment complexity has been shown.

The rest of paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we describe the large-scale D-MIMO system model and precoding method. In Section III, we provide numerical results for the achievable downlink SE and discussions. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In traditional cellular systems, the antennas are collocated at specific location of a BS whereas in D-MIMO systems the APs with multiple antennas are geographically spread over the region, in a well-planned or random fashion in a D-MIMO system as shown in Fig. 1. Let N APs connected to CPU through high-capacity fronthaul links (e.g., fiber-optic cables) be serving K randomly distributed UEs. It is also known as cell-free massive MIMO system where each UE is coherently served by multiple APs. It is assumed that APs are equipped with M antennas and UEs have single antenna, nonetheless

it is straightforward to generalize the equations suitably for multi-antenna UEs. The following variables are defined for $n, z = 1, \dots, N$ APs, $j, k = 1, \dots, K$ UEs. Let q_k be the information bearing data symbol to be transmitted to the k -th UE, where $E\{q_k q_j\} = \delta_{jk}$, where $\delta_{jk} = 1$ for $j = k$, $\delta_{jk} = 0$ otherwise. $\mathbf{h}_{kn} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times M}$ represent the complex-valued channel coefficients between the n -th AP and the k -th UE, \mathbf{q}_k is the data symbol intended for the k -th UE, then, the transmitted data signal from the n -th AP to all the UEs can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}_n = \sum_{k=1}^K \omega_{kn} \mathbf{q}_k, \quad (1)$$

where $\omega_{kn} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the precoding vector. More APs involved in coherent transmission to a given UE results in higher degree of diversity. On the other hand, from the network perspective, more UEs to be served increases the complexity of the processing schemes. Given that APs can exchange information with the other APs and CPU through a perfect fronthaul network, the processing throughout the network can be conducted at the CPU by using the information from the whole network, e.g., large-scale fading coefficients. Alternatively some APs can perform precoding on behalf of the serving clusters, or each AP can independently do local precoding based on their local observations.

A. Access Point Selection and Clustering

UE-centric AP selection/clustering method has been set in which each UE is served by a subset of APs, typically the ones that provide a sufficiently high Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR). That subset is partially overlapping between neighboring UEs and thus the APs cannot always be divided into disjoint sets, as is the case in conventional cellular networks. The method in [16] selects the APs with the best channel quality that contribute at least $\alpha\%$, e.g., 95%, towards the k -th UE as follows

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_k} \frac{h'_{kn}}{\sum_{z=1}^N h'_{kz}} \geq \alpha\%, \quad (2)$$

where $\{h'_{k1}, h'_{k2}, \dots, h'_{kN}\}$ is the set of large scale fading coefficients, which is the sum over M transmit antennas, sorted in descending order, and N_k is the cardinality of the UE-centric subset. The AP grouping can be performed centrally at the CPU having the information on the channel large-scale fading coefficients to all UE, or alternatively each AP can decide to be part of serving cluster of a given UE based on local observations. APs can have a limit of maximum number of UEs to serve, where APs will prioritize the UEs with the better channel gains.

B. Signal Transmission

Since the distributed APs jointly serve a given UE can have very different path gains to the UE, it is favorable to adjust the precoding weights for each antenna while considering each AP has a peak transmission power limit which is denoted by P_n . Single frequency network transmission is assumed network-wide with a bandwidth of B Hz, and the zero mean circularly

symmetric additive white Gaussian noise with variance σ_η^2 is given by η_k . Then, the equation formulating the received signal for k -th UE is as follows:

$$\mathbf{y}_k(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_k} \sqrt{P_n} \mathbf{h}_{kn} \boldsymbol{\omega}_{kn} \mathbf{q}_k + \sum_{j=1, j \neq k}^{N_k} \sum_{n=1}^{N_j} \sqrt{P_n} \mathbf{h}_{jn} \boldsymbol{\omega}_{jn} \mathbf{q}_j + \eta_k, \forall k, \quad (3)$$

where first term is the intended signal received from the APs in the dedicated serving cluster of the UE, and the other terms denote the inter-UE interference and noise term, respectively. Then the Signal-to-Interference-Noise-Ratio (SINR, γ) of the given UE is represented as

$$\gamma_k(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{|\sum_{n=1}^{N_k} \sqrt{P_n} \mathbf{h}_{kn} \boldsymbol{\omega}_{kn}|^2}{\sum_{j=1, j \neq k}^{N_k} |\sum_{n=1}^{N_j} \sqrt{P_n} \mathbf{h}_{jn} \boldsymbol{\omega}_{jn}|^2 + \sigma_\eta^2}, \forall k, \quad (4)$$

and eventually the per-UE downlink Spectral Efficiency (SE, r) is found as

$$r(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 [1 + \gamma_k(\boldsymbol{\omega})]. \quad (5)$$

C. Precoding

Conventional multi-user MIMO implementations typically rely on Frequency-Division Duplexing (FDD) operation whereas massive MIMO systems with Time-Division Duplexing (TDD) operation bring large improvements in throughput which result from the strong spatial multiplexing achieved by appropriately shaping the signals sent out and received by the serving antennas. By applying precoding to all antennas, the network can ensure constructive interference among signals at the locations of the intended UEs, and destructive almost everywhere else. In this section, we present reciprocity-based UE-centric IADZF method and compare with CZF. An attractive property of the method is that each precoding done in clusters are interference-aware, i.e., consider minimizing the interference that will create to other clusters.

a) Centralized Zero-Forcing (CZF): Assuming all APs form a single cluster, i.e., can transmit signals to any UE, and precoding is done in the central entity, CPU. Let us represent the received signal in terms of conformable channel gain ($\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times NM}$) and precoding ($\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{NM \times K}$) matrices as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_1^H & \mathbf{H}_2^H & \cdots & \mathbf{H}_K^H \end{bmatrix}^H \mathbf{W}\mathbf{q}, \quad (6)$$

where $(\cdot)^H$ is the conjugate transpose operation, $\mathbf{H}_k = [\mathbf{h}_{k1} \ \mathbf{h}_{k2} \ \cdots \ \mathbf{h}_{kN}]$ is the channel gain matrix for the k -th UE with the all serving APs. Then, the precoding matrix (\mathbf{W}) can be found by

$$\mathbf{W} = \underset{\mathbf{X}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{H}\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{I}\| \quad (7)$$

$$= [\mathbf{H}^H \mathbf{H}]^{-1} \mathbf{H}^H \approx [\hat{\mathbf{H}}^H \hat{\mathbf{H}} + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}]^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{H}}^H, \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H} + \tilde{\mathbf{H}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Gamma} = E\{\tilde{\mathbf{H}}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}\}$ is the error covariance matrix.

b) Interference Aware Distributed Zero Forcing (IADZF): APs form clusters in a CPU-centric or UE-centric way, and serve UEs inside the given cluster, but creates interference to the UEs outside of the cluster. Herein, the precoding weights are calculated for each cluster separately. Let $\mathbf{H}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{K_i \times N_i M}$ be the channel gain matrix between the N_i APs and K_i UEs in the i -th cluster (C_i) composed of N_i APs, $\mathbf{G}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{(K-K_i) \times N_i M}$ be the interference channel matrix between the APs inside C_i and UEs outside C_i , and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_i M \times K_i}$ be the corresponding precoding matrix for C_i . The received signal vector for the UEs inside and outside C_i are found as $\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{H}_i \hat{\mathbf{W}}_i \mathbf{q}_i$ and $\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{G}_i \hat{\mathbf{W}}_i \mathbf{q}_i$, respectively. Then, $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_i$ can be found by minimizing the interference to outside of the cluster as following

$$\hat{\mathbf{W}}_i = \underset{\mathbf{X}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_i \\ \mathbf{G}_i \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{X} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \right\| \quad (9)$$

$$= [\mathbf{H}_i^H \mathbf{H}_i + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_i]^{-1} \mathbf{H}_i^H \\ \approx [\hat{\mathbf{H}}_i^H \hat{\mathbf{H}}_i + \boldsymbol{\Gamma}_i + \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_i]^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{H}}_i^H, \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_i = \mathbf{G}_i^H \mathbf{G}_i$ is the interference covariance matrix. If clusters are disjoint, i.e., CPU-centric in which clusters don't have common AP, thus each separate precoding vectors ($\hat{\mathbf{W}}_i$) are independent, eventually, generalized precoding matrix (\mathbf{W}) is direct sum of each $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_i$ and off-diagonal blocks are zero matrices. Nonetheless, UE-centric grouping necessitates K clusters that may have common APs which creates dependency between individual precoding vectors for each cluster. The generalized precoding matrix (\mathbf{W}) is composed of K UE-specific precoding vectors, $\mathbf{W}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{NM \times 1}$ as

$$\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{W}_1 \ \mathbf{W}_2 \ \cdots \ \mathbf{W}_K] \quad (11)$$

$$= [\mathbf{v}_1^H \ \mathbf{v}_2^H \ \cdots \ \mathbf{v}_N^H]^H, \quad (12)$$

where the calculated weights of $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_k M \times 1}$ are the non-zero elements of \mathbf{W}_k . Due to this dependency, precoding weights need to be normalized as

$$\mathbf{W} = \frac{\mathbf{W}}{\max_n \|\mathbf{v}_n\|}, \quad (13)$$

which limits the solution with a sub-optimal precoding but ensures that none of the AP exceeds maximum power transmission limit.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, performance of the large scale D-MIMO system depicted in Fig. 2 is analyzed in a downlink indoor scenario over an area of $100m \times 100m$ with $A = 1000$ blockers which creates a blocking environment with maximum size of $2m \times 3m$ and minimum size of $0.5m \times 1m$, are randomly distributed. The performance has been evaluated for different number of APs regularly deployed and $K = 20$ and $K = 40$ uniformly distributed UEs. It is assumed that UEs have single-antenna transceivers, and each AP is equipped with $M = M_v \times M_h$ antenna elements, where M_v and M_h are the vertical and horizontal antenna elements, respectively.

Fig. 2. Reference deployment scenario with $N = 100$ APs, 20 UEs, and 1000 blockers.

Nonetheless, it is assumed that M elements form a single subarray and contributes only with array gain.

Network performance is assessed for different frequency range from sub-6 GHz bands to sub-THz bands. The configuration parameters used in the simulations are given in Table I. Perfect channel estimation and fronthaul is assumed. RF imperfections, hardware impairments, phase noise, power amplifier nonlinearities are omitted from the scope of this work.

TABLE I
SIMULATION MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Model Specification		
Frequency range (GHz)	3.5	28	100
Bandwidth (MHz)	50	200	5500
AP max power (P_m)	13 dBm		
Number of subarrays	1		
Vertical antenna elements	2	4	8
Horizontal antenna elements	4	8	16
Propagation Model	3GPP InH [17]		
Duplexing	TDD with 50% downlink		
AP Noise Figure (dB)	5	7	10
Overhead ratio	1:3		

Fig. 3 shows the SE per UE with respect to the different number of APs deployed in the given area for different operating frequency bands and corresponding bandwidths. IADZF method has been applied over UE-centric clusters, which can have common APs, composed of APs selected with $\alpha = 95\%$ clustering method, and it has been shown that it can achieve the performance of CZF applied when all APs serves each UE. Two methods converge if the number of APs is much larger than the number of UEs. It can be noted that centralized precoding is implicitly interference-aware. Moreover, performance gains decrease at higher frequencies due to increased path loss, where signal penetration over blockers also decreases. Performance of Maximum Ratio Transmission (MRT) has also been evaluated for comparison, which is outperformed by interference-aware ZF method and performs almost the same for different frequency bands.

Fig. 4 shows the performance of (a) IADZF and (b) distributed interference-unaware conventional ZF method for different cluster sizes, $N_k = 1, N_k = 4, \alpha = 95\%$ grouping

Fig. 3. SE performance comparison of IADZF, CZF and MRT for different cluster sizes in a scenario with 1000 blockers and 20 UEs operating at 3.5, 28, and 100 GHz.

Fig. 4. SE Performance comparison of interference (a) aware / (b) unaware UE-centric ZF for different cluster sizes in a scenario for 20 UEs operating at 28 GHz.

approach, and all AP JT, operating at 28 GHz. It has been shown that more APs in UE-centric subsets utilizing IADZF method, brings more precoding gain, increases the performance, which has a potential of substantial gains. However, bigger clusters have degraded performance if the ZF in clusters is interference unaware, i.e., don't minimize their interfering signals to other clusters.

Fig. 5 shows the cumulative distribution function (cdf) of SINR values for a scenario in which 49 APs serve to 20 UEs. Various UE cluster sizes have been considered, e.g., $N_k =$

Fig. 5. SINR cdfs for interference aware UE-centric ZF in a scenario of $N = 49$ APs and $K = 20$ UEs. Results are evaluated at (a) 3.5 GHz, (b) 28 GHz, and (c) 100 GHz.

1, $N_k = 4$, $\alpha = 95\%$ grouping approach, and $N_k = 49$, i.e., all AP JT. It has been demonstrated that more coordinated APs increases the performance. Small size clusters perform similar at all frequency bands, however the potential gain of more APs is much more at lower frequencies since some of the APs become dominant as frequency increases. Nonetheless, more coordinated APs can enable the cell-edge UEs, e.g., 5% having positive SINR. Lower frequency bands are reliable, but spectrum limited, that is why bigger clusters having more antenna elements are preferable, since higher SE and capacity enhancements are desired. However, it should be noted that, collocating massive number of antenna elements can be hard due to e.g., physical size limitations and more distributed APs needs more coordination. Small clusters can still provide good enough SE performance on the average, and particularly can utilize the high bandwidth at high frequency bands.

In order to provide a robust access link against path loss and blocking at high frequencies, distribution and coordination of antennas is a promising candidate. Followingly, it can be argued that how much distribution is needed and Fig. 7 demonstrates the SE performance averaged over $K = 40$ UEs with respect to the number of deployment locations (L), where $N = 64 \times M$ antennas are distributed over $L = \{1, 4, 16, 64\}$ locations. Herein, it is assumed that there are still 64 subarrays, each formed by M antenna elements. A deployment example of $L = 4$ locations at which each AP has $16 \times M$ antennas is also depicted in Fig. 6. It has been shown that collocated or fully distributed ($L = 64$) deployments perform similar for all AP JT in terms of SE, semi-distributed deployment ($L = 4$) performs almost same with the fully

Fig. 6. Reference example of partially distributed deployment of $N = 64$ antennas onto $L = 4$ locations including 40 UEs, and 1000 blockers.

Fig. 7. Performance comparison for collocated ($L = 1$), partially ($L = \{4, 16\}$) and fully distributed ($L = 64$) deployments for different operating frequencies. (a) all AP JT, (b) AP selection in small clusters, $N_i = \{1, 4\}$.

distributed deployment. Herein, there is a trade-off between implementation complexity and deployment complexity. All AP JT can still achieve high SE values by collocating the antennas, but it is more complex in terms of implementation. In case of less diversity and antennas, i.e., small clusters ($N_i = \{1, 4\}$), implementation will be easier, nonetheless more distribution is needed for comparable performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have investigated the performance of IADZF method in large scale D-MIMO system where a subset of APs jointly serving to the UEs in a UE-centric manner, and its performance is compared with CZF with all AP JT. It has been shown that more APs increases precoding gain and spectral efficiency, but interference awareness is essential for distributed precoding. Small size clusters performs similar at all frequency bands, however the potential gain of more APs is much more at lower frequencies since some of the APs

become dominant as frequency increases. A trade-off has been shown between implementation complexity and deployment complexity. All AP JT can achieve high performance with a collocated deployment but needs more complex implementation. In case of JT with small subsets, implementation will be easier, however more distribution is needed for comparable performance.

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